

ATMO ACCESS
Access to Atmospheric Research Facilities

Deliverable D7.1 Interim Evaluation Report on Access Programme

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1 Introduction

The ATMO-ACCESS project is the organized response of distributed atmospheric research facilities for developing a pilot for a new model of Integrating Activities. ATMO-ACCESS will deliver a series of recommendations for establishing a comprehensive and sustainable framework for access to distributed atmospheric Research Infrastructures (RI), ensuring integrated access to and optimised use of the services provided.

To achieve this, ATMO-ACCESS is developing a programme of access to several atmospheric Research Infrastructures individually, or in combination. To enable the development of this access programme, the objectives of WP7, which are implemented through the WP's respective Tasks, have been defined as to:

- Design of a realistic and comprehensive access programme (Preparation phase)
- Effectively and timely plan the opening of access calls (Launching phase)
- Measure success of access calls and optimize the access programme (Monitoring phase)

Within this framework, this document reports on the interim evaluation of the access programme. It does so, according to Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that consider both the users, and the access providers. Within this context, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined as a type of performance measurements evaluating the success of an organization or of a particular activity in which it engages, in this case the access programme designed and implemented by the ATMO-ACCESS Consortium.

The purpose of this document is to **contribute to the comprehensive monitoring of the access programme** (both in response to the access calls, and in regards to the success of the projects in the calls), to **help inform the ongoing refinement of the programme** based on these insights, including the scope and scheduling of associated future calls.

Accordingly, this deliverable falls with the scope of “Task 7.3 Monitoring Phase – Measuring and responding to the success of the access programme”, whilst reflecting on the activities carried out so far in both “Task 7.1 Preparation Phase”, and “Task 7.2 Launch Phase”. It considers and consolidates interests, metrics and input from other relevant WPs (most potently innovative modes of access explored in WP4 -6). The contents of this document will also feed into WP8, within which recommendations regarding future implementation of access modalities will be given.

It should be noted at this point that the parallel development of processes for documenting the access and defining KPIs made both by SAMU and by WP7, as well as construction of the philosophy underpinning the possible alternative approaches to sustainable access and of the access programme itself, has necessarily led to developing parallel methodologies and possible inconsistencies in data availability. This should not be seen as a flaw in the process, but a feature of the novel approach to exploring sustainable access with advantages in being able to recommend enhancements to the process and metrics for evaluation.

2 Methodology

This interim report on the evaluation of the access programme focuses on the evaluation of key performance metrics relating to the success, popularity and applicability of the access programme, starting with a review of the data gathered after the conclusion of Access Calls 1 -3.

Table 1: Number of calls, type of call, and related time scheduled assessed in D7.1 (in terms of KPIs).

In defining these KPIs the CYI team in charge of this deliverable has followed the general principles of good practice as this has been identified by the European Commission¹, hence ensuring that KPIs are *RACER*, i.e.:

- **Relevant**, realistic and in line with the objectives of the project.
- **Accepted** by the Consortium and relevant stakeholders, by ensuring that the purpose the indicator serves is well defined.
- **Credible** for non-experts, unambiguous and easy to interpret. Indicators should be as simple and robust as possible.
- **Easy** to monitor at low cost and effort.
- **Robust** against manipulation.

Following the methodology described in Task 7.3, key performance indicators are defined at the early stages of the project, and are periodically reviewed (D7.1, D7.2) to ensure that they remain fit for purpose and relevant.

To define the KPIs, the following methodological steps were followed:

- Identify the aspects of the access programme that require evaluation
- Determine the metrics to use to monitor these aspects
- Set realistic targets to be able to verify if success has been achieved

In line with the above principles, the access programme KPIs examined in this interim evaluation report fall into two key categories:

- User Metrics:** which are set in place to reflect who and how many the users are
- Access Provision Metrics:** which are set in place to reflect the type of facilities and categories of services requested, as well as the modalities of access used

These are examined in sections 3 and 4 of this document respectively.

Finally, in section 5, conclusions are drawn based on the findings examined in sections 3 & 4, as recommendations to be considered by WP8. In addition, suggestions for further quantitative and qualitative performance criteria and metrics are proposed. These are to be considered in the final evaluation report (D7.2), and to be taken into account in planning for the long-term implementation of new access modalities proposed through ATMO-ACCESS. These consider both an internal perspective (i.e. success factors for the access modalities' sustainable long-term offering by RIs, such as cost-benefit efficiency for the access provider), and an external, user-centric perspective (i.e. considering the attractiveness of the modality and its ease of use).

¹ "Better regulation Toolbox", produced by the European Commission complementing the "Better Regulation Guidelines". Accessed from [Better regulation: guidelines and toolbox \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/better-regulation/) on 01 June 2023.

3. List of KPIs

3.1 Methodology

The list of TNA KPIs has been built based on the information (excel files) that have been prepared by SAMU for each of the three (3) first TNA calls. A detailed list of TNA KPIs is provided in Annex 2 (for Call#1: 4 excel files), Annex 3 (for Call#2: 2 excel files), and Annex 4 (for Call#3: 2 excel files).

It should be noted that in compiling the KPIs analysis, a number of methodological issues have arisen, relating to changes in the ways data was monitored, labelled and processed across different access calls. Such changes reflect the evolution of the application, evaluation and data collection processes as ATMO-ACCESS has developed. In order to perform a benchmark analysis for the 3 calls, for the purposes of this deliverable, similar KPIs that have been monitored by the calls, and the raw data provided for these, have been considered. Relevant findings from this analysis are reported in the Table in section 6 below.

However, based on the findings of this interim evaluation, it is acknowledged that these issues need to be rectified. It intends to do so and this is the intention for future calls, through recommendations made throughout this document, aimed at adopting a standardized monitoring and processing methodology across TNA Calls. Some of these recommendations are summarised below (with further details included in sections 4- 7):

- The same KPIs should be consistently monitored and processed across all calls, and their naming should be consistent throughout
- **Overall, an agreed template for the compilation of KPIs should be generated at the beginning of an access programme. This should be made available for use by those responsible for monitoring and processing the data for each call**, to ensure consistency, and traceability (i.e. providing means of verification for the calculations made). Similarly, an accompanying template for the display of graphics should be made available (as currently different graphs have been made for the same KPI across different calls).

3.2 List of KPIs measured for the 3 calls

The below Table 2 brings together information on **15 KPIs from ACCEPTED TNA applications** as follow:

1. **USER METRICS for the leader: 7 KPIs** (Gender, Nationality, Profile, Field of Expertise, Institution status, Institution country, New user)
2. **ACCESS PROVISION METRICS: 8 KPIs** (Success rate, category of access, proposed form of access, Host Facility information, Host Facility type, Similar Facility in user country, Type of access, mode of access)

More information on each of the KPI is presented in Section 3.

Table 2: List of available KPIs for each of the three first TNA calls.

KPI	KPI available for Call #1	KPI available for Call #2	KPI available for Call #3
USER METRICS			
Gender of Leader (M/F/Other)	YES	YES	YES
Leader (nationality)	YES	YES	NO
Leader User Profile (A to D)	YES	YES	YES
Leader Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	YES	YES	NO
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	YES	YES	YES
Institution (address and country)	YES	YES	YES
New user (yes/no)	YES	YES	NO
ACCESS PROVISION METRICS (Accepted TNA)			

Current Stage (Accepted/Rejected)	YES	YES	YES
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	YES	YES	YES
Proposed mode / form of access (single/multiple)	YES	NO	YES
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	YES	YES	YES
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)	YES	YES	YES
Is there a facility similar to that/all those you wish to utilize in the country where you work? (yes/no)	YES	NO	YES
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	YES	YES	YES
Mode of Access (Market, Tech, Excellence, Training)	NO	YES	NO

For each call (1, 2, 3), a separate sheet was prepared for either USER METRICS or ACCESS PROVISION METRICS. Data from excel files received from the SAMU was then processed to fill each of these sheets. Some KPIs could not be calculated because the excel files did not contain the information to calculate them. Data from KPIs was taken as it is from the excel files.

4 User Metrics (PIs of Accepted TNAs)

4.1 Gender

Gender balance in the access team leadership is not achieved (on average 2/3 Males and 1/3 Females). However, there is a tendency towards improved gender balance (constant increase of female representation from 31% (Call 1) to 41% (Call 3)).

4.2 PI Nationality & Country of Institution's Affiliation

These two (2) KPIs have been summarized for all calls in the table below.

The information obtained by these 2 KPIs is often similar (i.e. Nationality and Country affiliation of PIs are similar). Almost two thirds of the PIs (nationality and country of institution's affiliation) are from the EU. Non-EU but based in Europe institutions represent ca. 20% of the applications; 11% are non-European institutions. The PIs' institutions are mainly located in the largest (most populated) European countries (Germany, France, Italy, UK). Nevertheless, smaller countries (e.g. Finland, Switzerland) are also active. The same picture can be drawn for the nationality of PI, with one exception (China). The contribution of institutions from EU widening countries² (21) represents only 20% of the EU institutions.

² List of EU widening countries at this link : https://rea.ec.europa.eu/horizon-europe-widening-who-should-apply_en#:~:text=All%20organisations%20eligible%20in%20Horizon,in%20FP7%20and%20H2020%20projects.

Country of origin of Accepted TNA PIs (ALL CALLS)

As calculated from the sum of call 1+2 (this data is missing in call 3)

TOTAL count : 102

Breakdown : EU : 72 / European non-EU : 9 / Non-European : 21

Affiliation country of Accepted TNA PIs (ALL CALLS)

As calculated from the sum of call 1+2+3

TOTAL count : 148

Breakdown : EU : 102 / European non-EU : 29 / Non-European : 17

4.3 PI User Profile

This KPI has been calculated based on the data from 3 calls and information received by PI of accepted TNA projects.

Three (3) out of 5 categories (undergraduate, engineers/technicians, others) do contribute marginally to the statistics (only 6%) for a total of 149 TNA PIs.

Recommendation:

On the other hand, a better refinement of the category “Expert scientists” should be proposed in order to better capture the granularity of this population which represents 75% of the PIs.

Breakdown could be done, for instance, as function of the seniority following, for instance, the ERC classification (Early Stage vs Advanced).

The term “young scientist” (counted as Bonus in the evaluation of the TNA) is not clearly visible here (could be either Post-graduate or Expert Scientists).

4.4 PIs Field of expertise

This KPI has been calculated based on the data from 3 calls and information received by PIs of accepted TNA projects..

One out of 8 categories (ENV-ATMO) does contribute to 92% of the total population. Unsurprisingly, ATMO-ACCESS calls have mainly attracted users from the atmospheric science community. The specific research of multidisciplinary TNA projects will be addressed more specifically in Call 6 (autumn 2023).

Recommendation:

As already suggested in Section 3.3, a better breakdown should be considered here to better capture the granularity of the users who have responded to the calls so far.

The first level of refinement would be to capture the different RI communities (e.g. ICOS, ACTRIS) and possibly towards the 3 parameters monitored in ACTRIS (e.g. Aerosols, Clouds, Trace Gases) or monitoring (in-situ vs remote sensing).

4.5 Affiliation Profile (PIs)

This KPI has been calculated based on the data from 3 calls and information received by PIs of accepted TNA projects.

The three main categories represent 95% of the different types of Organizations. “University/Higher Education” represents more than half of the users; 30% come from Public Research Organizations and 9% of users come from SMEs. (Total TNA considered = 149)

Recommendation:

Further analysis on the Innovation potential of facilities: given the small number of TNAs from SMEs (14 out of 149), it would be strategic to identify which facilities are the most requested, so as to better assess the most attractive ones for the private sector. A specific call for private sector user was issued in Q2-2023 and will be further analysed in the frame of the Task 6.3 Innovation pilot.

Considering different constraints such as the language barrier, very few public authorities have applied for TNA projects. A specific call for public authorities will be released in Q3-2023.

4.6. New user (PI)

This KPI has been calculated based on the data from 2 first calls and information received by PIs of accepted TNA projects (for this KPI, information is missing for Call #3).

With 72% of new users, ATMO-ACCESS is engaging a large community of end-users.

Recommendation:

More advanced KPI analysis could be proposed here to better capture the profile of the new users (e.g. Post-Graduates? Gender?). The selection criteria and scoring established by the SSC considered this category as “bonus” point, in addition to the main scientific excellence parameters. Therefore, it would be useful to understand whether other factors, such as the communication strategy, have played a role in the obtention of these results.

5. Access Provision metrics

5.1. Success Rate

The KPI “Success Rate” was calculated from the data from the 3 calls.

The graphics show a decrease in the success rate from the first (92%) to the third call (66%). This was the result of a readjustment of the success rate made by the Strategic TNA and VA Board (WP7) in charge of the selection process, in order to make the TNA programme more competitive, in line with the EC guidelines. Overall, the success rate of the three calls is of 79%.

5.2. Type of Services Service Requested

The KPI “Type of Services Service Requested” was calculated from the data from the 3 calls.

The request for access for Research/Innovation purposes remains by far the main request (85% on average).

Recommendation:

A breakdown of success rate between the different type of services would be interesting to perform. A better breakdown between “Research” and “Innovation” should be considered to better capture the two and refine this KPI with better granularity. Technical services’ requests have increased over the calls; this needs to be assessed as well. A more in-depth analysis of KPIs with Technical Services would help to identify the profile of the Applicant (e.g. are these services requested by SMEs?) and the type of facilities which is accessed (e.g. are these the services provided by Central Facilities?) .

The training component has attracted less users so far/ Application requesting access for Training purposes have encountered a lower success rate. It would be important to understand the reason. For example by making an analysis of the success rate of applications with a Training component only (e.g. are they sufficiently competitive in terms of Scientific Excellence?). Specific calls on training are developed in WP4 and will be analysed in D7.2.

5.3. Multiple Access Requests

By multiple access, it is meant a request to access two or more facilities in the framework of one single TNA application, for the purpose of the same research project. The KPI “Multiple Access Request” was calculated from the data from two calls out of three (Call #1 and Call #3).

“Single Access” means of TNA request to access a single Facility. “Multiple Access” means a TNA request to access at the same time multiple Facilities

The vast majority of access is single. Only 8% (9 out of 111 TNAs) are multiple access.

Recommendation:

A better assessment of the type of multiple access TNA (which facility? type of access? etc) would help to understand the rationale behind these requests and therefore the motivations why this KPI is strategic to monitor (multidisciplinary research, use of mobile platforms, etc). This might be most interesting KPI to investigate when analysing the data from the multidisciplinary TNA call.

5.4. Host Facilities

This KPI was calculated as the sum of all accepted TNA projects from the 3 calls (i.e. total of 149). The breakdown per type of facility is also given.

OBS

CL

ASC

MOB

This KPI allows assessing the facilities with currently the highest number of access units provided in the project. More precisely:

- **OBS (observational platforms):** Considering that the largest part of the available facilities falls into this category, the numbers show that 7 (out of 18) have hosted 6 or more TNAs. 6 OBS facilities have hosted only 2 TNAs.
- **ASC (atmospheric simulation chambers):** Numbers show a fairly good distribution of hosted TNA projects between the different ASC facilities (total of 38 TNAs for ASC)
- **CL (central laboratories):** The main contributors are ISOLAB and CiGAS CH (17 out of total 20 TNAs),
- **MOB (mobiles platforms):** Most of the TNA projects were hosted by the USRL mobile facility (10 out of 14)

Recommendation:

A further analysis of the most accessed facilities inside the TNA programme could be performed to assess the rationale behind this number of access (e.g. in terms of attractiveness, visibility, etc.).

5.5. Type of access requested (physical access (PA), remote access (RA), combined access (PA+RA))

This KPI was calculated as the sum of all accepted TNA from the 3 calls.

There is a clear tendency in this KPI towards a combination of combined Access which is progressing from 31 to 50% from Call 1 to Call 3 and becomes the second largest after physical access. Remote Access was high for Call 1 (which took place during the COVID period) but surprisingly remained high (e.g. Call 3) although COVID was over. A specific call ([Call 4](#)) is has been issued in M23 (February 2023) to promote this access mode. Data related to this call will be analysed in D7.2.

6. Alignment between the TNA scoring and KPIs

In order to achieve targets of KPIs by the end of the project, it is of critical importance to assess if they are properly accounted in the TNA scoring that is currently used during the evaluation process of TNA applications.

TNA SCORING	Alignment with monitored KPIs
SECTION 1 - TECHNICAL NEED	
(1.a) Frequency of the technical need (5 points)	No
(1.b) Training for the staff using the instrument (5 points)	Yes. Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)
(1.c) References and experience of the user group (5 points)	No
SECTION 2 - SCIENTIFIC RELEVANCE	
(2.a) Relevance of the instrument	No
(2.b) Interest to the scientific community	No
(2.c) Dissemination plan: availability and use of data	No
SECTION 3 - BONUS POINTS	
Gender diversity /empowerment (1 point)	Partial. Gender of PI only
Collaboration and access to new Users (1 point)	Partial. New user of the PI only
Involvement of students / young scientists (1 point)	Partial. PI User Profile only

6.1 List of recommendations towards achieving KPI targets of USER METRICS

- **KPI “Gender Balance”**. Only accounted for the PI/Applicant. The monitoring of this KPI should be extended to all users. This is done in some calls, but it should be adopted as a common practice for all calls.
- **KPI “Nationality of the PI”** (and / or Institution). Not accounted in the review. Many EU programmes (e.g. COST Actions, Horizon Europe) do account for, and give priority to, EU Widening Countries. This could be considered in future TNA calls and can be easily monitored by the KPI “Nationality of the PI” already in place.
- **KPI “User Profile”**. Only accounted for the PI/Applicant. The monitoring of this KPI is recommended to be extended to all users. Currently this KPI does not account for the “Involvement of students / young scientists” of the user team. A better alignment between the two would help to monitor (and better engage) early career scientists. E.g. does the KPI “Post-Graduate” align completely with “Young Scientist”?
- **KPI “PI Field of Expertise”**. Not accounted in the review. This will be partially considered in call #6 (multi-disciplinary). Nevertheless, there is currently no mechanism (e.g. bonus points) to better engage users from other fields of expertise to access ATMO-ACCSS facilities and promote multi-disciplinarity.
- **KPI “Institution Status”**. Not accounted in the review. May be considered (e.g. as bonus point) if there is a need to better engage new stakeholders. This is partly accounted by the “Trans-national access for private sector” (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/trans-national-access-for-private-sector/>). However, there is currently no KPI monitoring mechanism for this specific TNA call (aggregated to other calls).

6.2 List of recommendations towards achieving KPI targets of ACCESS PROVISION METRICS

- **KPI “Main category of requested service/s (R&I services, Technical services, Training services only)”**. This will be accounted in the technical need section of TNA scoring. However, the TNA scoring provides only points for one of them (Training).
- **KPI “Proposed mode / form of access (single/multiple)”**. Not accounted in the review. It is a meaningful KPI only if we encourage multiple access; this may be considered in the TNA scoring (e.g. as bonus point).
- **KPI “Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)”**. Not accounted in the review. There should be a mechanism (e.g. as bonus point) to encourage the use on new facilities (i.e. those provided TNA for the first time in ATMO-ACCESS). Unless this KPI has other functions and aims to identify the best performers. In all cases, a better description of the KPI would help to understand the targets to reach.
- **KPI “Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)”**. Not accounted in the review. A possible approach could be to have calls with multiple access with synergies between the different types of facilities (e.g. OBS + MOB).
- **KPI “Is there a facility similar to that/all those you wish to utilize in the country where you work? (yes/no)”**. Not accounted in the review. KPI targets should be clearer (understanding of motivations apply for a TNA).
- **KPI “Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)”**. Not accounted in the review. This aspect has been promoted and taken into account in call #4 (remote access).

- **KPI “Mode of Access (Market-driven, Technical-driven, Excellence-driven, Training)”**. This was set in call #2 but not monitored afterwards.

7. Conclusions & Recommendations

As highlighted in the Introduction, the purpose of this document was to:

- **contribute to the comprehensive monitoring of the access programme**
- **help inform the continuous refinement of the programme**

To achieve these goals, a thorough analysis was performed on existing data compiled over the first 3 TNA calls.

As pointed out in Section 2 (Methodology), this compilation of data proved to be difficult: this was due to partially incomplete data, as well as to the fact that the scoring system has evolved throughout the calls, making it difficult to compare the calls. These two factors hindered the efficient and consistent analysis of KPIs across calls.

Despite this, a core of 14 KPIs were identified and further processed, in order to monitor the so-far provision of TNA by ATMO-ACCESS. These were equally distributed (7/7) towards USER METRICS and ACCESS PROVISION METRICS. The main conclusions from the analysis of these KPIs, and respective recommendations for their better monitoring in future, are as follows:

KPI	Conclusions	Recommendations
USER METRICS		
Gender (PI)	Tendency towards a better gender balance (constant increase of female representation from 31% (Call 1) to 41% (Call 3))	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only accounted for the PI. The monitoring of this KPI should be extended to all users. This is done in some calls (not all). This is important - a call full of balanced teams might be considered at least as good as a call with a balance in leaders
Nationality & Country of Affiliation (PI)	Two third of the PIs (nationality and country of affiliation) are from the EU. Non-EU Institutions represent ca. 20% of the applications; 11% for non-European institutions. The contribution of Institutions from EU widening countries represents only 20% of the EU institutions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To be better accounted in the review: Many EU programmes (e.g. COST Actions, Horizon Europe) do <u>account for, and give priority to, EU Widening Countries</u>. This could be considered in future TNA calls and can be easily monitored by the KPI “Nationality of the PI” already in place.
User Profile (PI)	Scientific Experts represent the vast majority of PIs (75%) followed by Post-Graduate (19%). The other staff categories are marginal (incl. public stakeholders, engineers/technicians, etc)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other categories (6% of leaders in total) could be merged as one entry (i.e. “other categories”) • Only accounted for the PI. Could be extended to all users. • Refinement of the category “Expert scientists”: Breakdown, for instance, as function of the seniority (age) following, for instance, the ERC classification (Early Stage vs Advanced). • The term “young scientist” (counted as Bonus in the evaluation of the TNA) not clearly visible here (could be either Post-graduate or Expert Scientists).
Field of expertise (PI)	One out of 8 categories (ENV-ATMO) does contribute to 92% of the total population.yet .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not accounted in the review (e.g. Priority to new Fields) • Better breakdown to capture the community of users from the atmospheric sciences domain (ENV-ATMO)
Affiliation Profile (PI)	Three main categories represent 95% of the different types of Organizations. Universities/Higher Education represent more than half. One third for Public Research Organizations. Only 9% are SMEs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More advanced data analysis to assess the interest of SMEs to better account for their (future) needs • Need to monitor the “fast-track” TNA for Private Sector (currently aggregated with other calls)
New user (PI)	With 72% of new users, ATMO-ACCESS is engaging a large community of end-users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More advanced data analysis to better capture 1) underlying factors that have brought this picture (e.g. communication strategy), and 2) the profile of the new users (e.g. Post-Graduates, Gender).
ACCESS PROVISION METRICS		

Success rate	Clear decrease in the success rate of TNA proposals (from 92% for Call 1 to 66% to Call 3). Average success rate around 80%.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aligned with the strategy of the STVB
Type of Service Requested	Access for Research/Innovation purposes remains by far the main request to access facilities (85% on average). Technical services growing over the calls (from 7 to 17%), the reasons could be investigated (better communication, more defined services from the Central Facilities). Training services are still marginal, and they are promoted in the review (5 points).	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Breakdown of the KPI between “Research” and “Innovation” (currently merged) More in-depth analysis of the Technical services (e.g. profile of the applicant, facilities, etc.) Need to better define the reasons behind the bonus points of Training in the TNA scoring (considered in the Technical Section, while not taken into account in the Scientific Section)
Multiple Access Request	Only 8% (9 out of 111 accepted TNAs) are multiple access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better assessment of multiple access TNA (which facility, type of access, etc) to capture the importance to monitor this KPI
Host Facilities	Identification of top performers (most requested facilities) for OBS, CL, and MOB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not accounted in the review. Mechanism to encourage the use of new facilities? Further analysis of the top/lower performers (attractiveness, visibility, etc.)
Type of access requested	Clear tendency towards a combination of Remote + Physical Access (progress from 31 to 50% from Call 1 to 3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Impact analysis of the advantages and difficulties of combined (physical and remote) access projects

7.1. Recommendations for future KPIs to better assess Project Impacts

Recommendations made in sections 4 and 5 outline the core KPIs, and considerations for their standardization, to better assess the performance of TNA calls that have, or are to, take place throughout the duration of the project. Further to these, this section recommends that additional KPIs be considered to be monitored by the Consortium, to better assess the potential impacts of the project, and how the TNA programme may be sustainably evolved beyond project duration. To ensure that the stakes of all parties involved can be fairly evaluated, the focus should be developing “inclusive metrics”, which take into account parameters that align with the interests of both the users and the access providers, for example:

- User-centric parameters: motivation / benefit from use, ease of use, cost of access (co-funding from the user)
- Access provider – centric parameters: cost/benefit analysis of access provision (including co-funding cost, and administrative burden), access outcomes (e.g. publications, and/or new products or services) - per modality of access, per variety of sector accessing the RI, per user type. For example, considering the publication of results will be an appropriate metric for access by academia / research communities, but it is not an appropriate metric for private sector access calls.

Considering how to integrate quantitative and qualitative metrics that inform the above parameters on the evaluation process for ATMO-ACCESS, could provide helpful insights on how the structure of a programme, which is attractive and beneficial to both users and access providers, could emerge, hence maximizing the potential of the project’s impact and the long-term sustainability of its results.

ANNEX 1: List of data used for the TNA KPIs

We report in the below tables that are used in the KPIs for each call

Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)

1	University and higher education
2	Public research
3	Public Authority
4	Small Medium Enterprise (SME)
5	Other industrial and/or profit private organization
6	Other, not specified

User Profile (A to D)

A	Expert scientist
B	Engineer, Technician
C	Post-graduate
D	Undergraduate
E	Other

Field of Expertise (I to VIII)

I	ENV-ATMO - Earth and environmental sciences/Atmospheric domain
II	ENG-TECH - Engineering and technology
III	CHEM - Chemistry
IV	ENV-ECOBIO - Earth and environmental sciences/Eco-biosphere
V	BIO-MED - Biological, medical sciences and biotechnology
VI	ENV-HYDRO - Earth and environmental sciences/Hydrosphere domain
VII	PHY - Physics astronomy, astrophysics
VIII	SOC - Social sciences

Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities + TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)

OBS	
ASC	
MOB	
CL	

ANNEX 2: TNA data collected for Call #1

We report in the below tables the TNA information gathered for Call#1. Fields in BLUE represent the KPIs that have been used to generate calls for this call.

CALL #1 (General Call)	Source of DATA for Call #1	KPI GRAPH from Call #1
#	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Submitted on (date)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Gender (M/F/Other)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Leader (nationality)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
User Profile (A to D)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Number of new users (number)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Does the user group include other members? (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Scientific field(s) and cross-disciplinarity (if any) of the project (ALL)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Proposed mode / form of access (single/multiple)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Is there a facility similar to that/all those you wish to utilize in the country where you work? (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Are you a recurrent user of the service? (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Current Stage (Accepted/Rejected)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_Received_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
TNA proposal	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	
Role in the group (Leader/Member)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	

Gender for each participant (M/F/Other)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
Naitionality for each participant (country)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
User Profile (A to D)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
New user (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
Private sector (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
External (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_ALL_User_Metrics	YES
#	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
appl #	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Name and Surname	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Gender (M/F/Other)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Leader (nationality)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
User Profile (A to D)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
New user (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Institution Name	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Access start date	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Access end date	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Potential flexibility of project dates?	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Does the user group include other members? (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Please upload the list of participants using the template in Attachment no. 1 to the Call documents	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Are there any references/publications of the user group in the domain of the application?	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
List 5 publications of the user group in the domain of the application	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Upload short CVs if no references are available	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Title & Acronym of the project	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	YES
Proposed mode / form of access (single/mutliple)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	YES
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	YES
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	YES
Is there a facility similar to that/all those you wish to utilize in the country where you work? (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Have you discussed the proposal with the access provider/s? (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	YES
Scientific objectives (max 3000 characters)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Experimental method and work plan (max 1300 characters)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Please specify if the access also involves some training to the participating user group and provide details	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Innovation Potential / impact (max 1500 characters)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
Are you a recurrent user of the service?	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_Metrics	
# in the group	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	

Role in the group (Member/Leader)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	
Gender for each participant (M/F/Other)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
Naitonality for each participant (country)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
User Profile (A to D)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
New user (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
Private sector (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES
External (yes/no)	ATMO_Call_1_Approved_Applications_User_Metrics	YES

ANNEX 3: TNA data collected for Call #2

CALL #2 (Green Deal)	Source of DATA for Call #2	KPI GRAPH from Call #2
Application ID	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Current Stage (Accepted/Rejected)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Gender (M/F/Other)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
User Profile (A to D)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Application ID	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Current Stage (Only Accepted)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Current State (Active)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)		YES
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Leader (nationality)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Number of new users (number)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Mode of Access (Market, Tech, Excellence, Training)	ATMO_Call_2_Accepted_Applications&Users_Metrics	YES
Application ID	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Current Stage (Accepted/Rejected)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Institution (address and country)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Affiliation (country)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES
Number of new users (number)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	ATMO_Call_2_ALL_Applications&Leaders_Metrics	YES

ANNEX 4: TNA data collected for Call #3

CALL #3 (General Call)	Source of DATA for Call #3	KPI GRAPH from Call #3
Application ID	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	
Role (Leader / Member)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	
Gender (M/F/Other)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	YES
Employing organization (country)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	YES
Employing organization - Legal status (1 to 6)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	YES
User Profile (A to D)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	YES
Field of Expertise (I to VIII)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def	YES
New user (yes / no)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def / Compiled information taken from another data source	
User (Internal / External)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def / Compiled information taken from another data source	YES
Is the user group leader a previous user of the facility? (yes/no)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def / Compiled information taken from another data source	YES
Did other users from the same country of the user leader access your facility in the past? (yes/no/other)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def / Compiled information taken from another data source	YES
Did other users from the same institution of the user leader access your facility in the past? (yes/no/other)	ATMO_3rd_Call_User_Data-2023_def / Compiled information taken from another data source	YES
Program Name	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Application ID (ATMO-TNA-3--0000000XXX)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Current Stage (Accepted/Rejected)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Roles (Applicant)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Institution status (1 to 6)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Institution (address and country)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Proposed mode / form of access (single/multiple)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Number of users (number)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Number of female users (number)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Number of new users (number)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Is the user group leader a previous user of the facility? (yes/no)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Did other users from the same country of the user leader access your facility in the past? (yes/no)	Applications_received_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Application ID (ATMO-TNA-3--0000000XXX)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Roles (Applicant)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Institution (Name)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Affiliation (country)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES

Institution status (1 to 6)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Institution (address and country)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Acronym of the project	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Host Facility/ies (List of Atmo-Access Facilities)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Host Facility/ies (TYPE - OBS - ASC - MOB - CL)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Proposed mode / form of access (single/multiple)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	
Type of access requested (PA, RA, PA+RA)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES
Main category of requested service/s (R&I, Tech, Training)	Applications_accepted_3rd_ATMO_call-2023_data	YES